

This cell volume ($n=4$) gives the theoretical value of density equal to 2.089 g cm^{-3} . The experimental value of density of the compound has been found to be 2.1 g cm^{-3} , which is in good agreement within the limits of experimental error.

The observed $\sin^2 \theta$ values for the coordination polymer correspond to the tetragonal system to give a unit cell with $a=8.46 \text{ \AA}$, $c=10.298 \text{ \AA}$ and cell volume $=737.257 \text{ \AA}^3$. Substitution of this cell volume ($n=4$) gives the theoretical value of density equal to 1.814 g cm^{-3} . The experimental value of density of the polymer determined by flotation method has been found to be 1.799 g cm^{-3} , which is also in good agreement within the limits of the experimental error.

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Sun Light Initiated Changes in Aqueous Solution of Lysine under Heterogeneous Conditions

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THE effect of different forms of radiations, i.e. ultraviolet, visible and sunlight on amino acids has been extensively studied by several workers¹⁻³ with different viewpoints and they have

reported the formation of amino acids, peptides, sugars and other related organic compounds. Lysine, an essential dietary amino acid required for growth and maintenance of nitrogen equilibrium, is chiefly found in the plant kingdom as protein and in free state. The effect of ultraviolet light, a main constituent of sunlight, on alkaline solution of lysine was studied by Morokuma² and he reported the formation of several products, i.e. aspartic acid, glycine, norvaline, norleucine and cadaverine. However studies concerning the effect of sunlight on aqueous solution of lysine do not exist in literature. Hence it was considered of interest to study the effect of sunlight on aqueous solutions of lysine in the presence and/or absence of certain phosphorus and nitrogenous additives mainly used as fertilisers and results have been presented in this communication.

Experimental

Sterilised (30 min at 20 lbs steam-pressure) aqueous solution of chromatographically homogeneous L-lysine (0.1 g/100 ml; B.D.H./E.M.) was exposed to sunlight ($6500'$, $25 \pm 5^\circ$) for varying periods upto 40 h in transparent sterilised glass vessels plugged with surgical cotton-wool in the presence or absence of sensitizers. The exposure was carried out under perfectly aseptic conditions. Extra-pure inorganic additives were used. The exposed solutions were drawn out aseptically, concentrated in a rotatory vacuum evaporator, examined for any microbial contamination by usual techniques⁶ and analysed chromatographically using Whatman No. 1, silica gel G or cellulose layer (MN 30J) as stationary phase and n-butanol-acetic acid-water (4:1:1, 4:1:5, v/v) or butanol-acetic acid-pyridine-water (15:3:10:12, v/v) as solvent systems. The authentic amino acids were run concurrently alongside the unknown spots as reference standards. For locating and characterising the resulting products, ninhydrin, alloxan, isatin (all 0.1% prepared in acetone) and Folin's reagent (0.2% 1,2-naphthaquinone-4-sulphonate in 5% aqueous sodium carbonate) were used as chromogenic reagents⁷ (Table 1).

DNP derivatives of provisionally identified as well as of authentic samples of amino acids were prepared and characterised as described earlier⁸. Thus the photolytic products were characterised by their comparison with authentic DNP acids, R_f values, m.p. of DNP acids, coincidence chromatography and also by specific chemical and spectral methods⁹.

Results and Discussion

Aqueous solution of lysine on exposure to sunlight for 5 h afforded four chromatographically separable and ninhydrin-distinct products (II, III, IV and VI), but on irradiating the reaction mixture for 40 h, only two products (IV and VI) could be detected from the exposed solutions. The results

NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF AMINO ACIDS

Sl. no.	Properties	Product obtained						
		I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII
1.	R _f value in (%)							
	(i) BAW	8.5	10.5	16.4	19.5	23.1	29.0	30.5
	(ii) BAPW	25.4	33.8	41.0	45.2	50.2	53.2	56.2
2.	Colour with ^a							
	(i) Ninhydrin	R	V	BV	RV	V	V	BV
	(ii) Isatin	—	BP	B	P	PB	BP	BP
	(iii) Folin's reagent	Y	B	G	GBr	GBr	G	GBr
3.	DNP Dvts.							
	(i) R _f value (%) ^b	—	—	12.0	36.1	—	50.7	—
	(ii) M.p. (°C)	—	—	186	202	—	177	—
4.	Fluorescence in uv black light lamp ^a	—	BW	W	W	BW	W	BW
5.	Co-chromatography one spot with amino acid	—	Orn	Asp	Gly	Threo	α-Ala	β-Ala
6.	Amino acid identified	—	Orn	Asp	Gly	Threo	α-Ala	β-Ala

^aV = Violet, B = blue, R = red, P = pink, G = green, Gr = grey, Br = brown, W = white, Y = yellow.

^bR_f in tert-amyl alcohol-3% ammonia, 1:1, v/v at 16±2°.

BAW solvent system: 1-butanol-acetic acid-water, 4:1:5, v/v; upper layer.

BAPW solvent system: 1-butanol-acetic acid-pyridine-water, 15:3:10:12, v/v at 16±2°.

of sunlight irradiation in aqueous solution of lysine in presence and absence of different additives are recorded in Table 2. It was observed that the effect of different additives used was in the order: urea > lysine > magnesium phosphate > ammonium sulphate > diammonium hydrogen phosphate, keeping in view the destruction of lysine. Out of the seven compounds, six have been characterised as ornithine (II), aspartic acid (III), glycine (IV), threonine (V), α-alanine (VI) and β-alanine (VII).

TABLE 2—RESULTS OF SUNLIGHT IRRADIATION (40 h) IN AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF LYSINE UNDER HETEROGENOUS CONDITIONS

Reaction mixture*	Products formed**						
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII
Lys + W	—	—	—	+	—	+	—
Lys + W + Mgp	++	+	+	—	+	—	+
Lys + W + DAp	—	—	T	T	—	—	—
Lys + W + AS	—	++	+	+	—	+	+
Lys + W + U	+++	—	+	+	—	—	+

*W = Water, Mgp = magnesium phosphate, DAp = diammonium hydrogen phosphate, AS = ammonium sulphate, U = urea. **T = Traces, (—) = not detected, (+) = fair yield, (++) = good yield, (+++) = high yield.

Morokuma¹ exposed lysine-HCl, dissolved in 4% Na₂CO₃ or 4% HCl to ultraviolet rays for 10 h and by chromatographic analysis revealed the formation of aspartic acid, glutamic acid, γ-amino-adipic acid, glycine, alanine, norvaline, norleucine and cadaverine. Thus the present study of sunlight initiated changes in aqueous solution of lysine in the presence or absence of additives shows interesting results as compared to the ultraviolet irradiation by Morokuma. While some of the amino

acids formed are the same others differ in their identity.

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Synthesis of Substituted Aromatic Amides

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HETEROAROMATICS, amide linkage, unsaturation and cyano group have been cited in literature as important functionalities for enhancing herbicidal activity¹. Vasilev and Terebenina² synthesised 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-halobenzoyl-pyra-

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